

CHALLENGES ENCOUNTERED AND LEADERSHIP SKILLS OF STUDENT LEADERS IN THE NEW NORMAL

DOI:

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Abstract:

This descriptive study examined the level of difficulties encountered by student leaders in the new normal in one of the medium sized Division in Region III for the School Year 2021-2022. It made use of a reliable self-made questionnaire to collect data from 91 Supreme Student Government Officers. The results showed that Most respondents were younger and female. Most of them attained are from medium school category and with higher average family monthly income. The level of difficulties encountered by the student leaders in the new normal vary at a certain level when they are grouped according to each area but have a "High Level" in over-all mean. Moreover, in terms of knowledge, respondents have high difficulty in discussing and facilitating the establishment of a plan of action in the new normal of education. While, in terms of ability, respondents' ability to utilize various platform to smoothly deliver the different programs, projects, and activities online faced a big challenge. Also, in terms of attitude, student leaders were becoming discomposed due to the changes brought by the pandemic. The level of difficulties encountered by the student leaders in the new normal according to knowledge, ability, and attitude vary at a certain level when they are grouped according to each variable but have a "High Level" in over-all mean. Additionally, when taken according to Knowledge and Ability, all variables obtained a highest mean in item no. 1 or using an accessible platform for convenience and smooth delivery of the different programs, projects, and activities in the new normal. Likewise, in terms of Attitude, all variables got a common highest mean in item no. 4 or managing their time and energy wisely in the new normal. All of the aforementioned variables in the difficulties encountered by the student leaders in the new normal showed no significant difference.

Keywords: Challenges encountered, leadership skills, student leaders, new normal, knowledge, ability, attitude

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

Today's student leaders are challenged with a range of difficulties daily, and how they respond to these issues defines their success or failure as Supreme Student Government leaders to a large extent. They are expected to be visionary to help every school succeed in managing day-to-day activities. Management and leadership in delivering programs, projects, and activities for the youth are two of the most significant and perplexing issues confronting today's student leaders.

As a Project Development Officer under the Youth Formation Division, in charge of the implementation of the different programs, projects, and activities for the youth, and one with the Department of Education's commitment to providing learners with quality basic education that is accessible, inclusive, and liberating through proactive leadership, shared governance, evidence-based policy standards, program responsive and relevant curricula, and highly competent and committed officials.

The YFD aims to develop the country's youth for societal growth and aspires to mold learners into proactive Filipinos who understand that society cannot succeed unless all its parts work together to address the nation's aspirations. Further, it is anchored in supporting the implementation of the K to 12 curricula by honing and complementing the following learning areas and skills: Societal Engagement, Technical Skills, Social Skills, Creativity and Innovation Skills, Affective skills, and Self Mastery Skills (DepEd, 2021).

The researcher observed that the student leaders of the Supreme Student Government encountered a lot of difficulties during the pandemic. Hence, the researcher is prompted to conduct this study to determine the level of difficulties encountered by student leaders in the new normal according to the areas knowledge, ability, and attitude and eventually find ways to sustain their courage and fortitude amidst challenges and difficulties they have encountered.

Current State of Knowledge

According to Sharice Johnson (2020), Student Program Leader at Milton Hershey School, Student leadership, just like any other type of leadership, doesn't end during a crisis but is more important during it. Student leaders can find their voice to help create a sense of hope, positivity, and inspiration for others. Creating a positive message inspires others, leading by example, and using their voice to establish trust and respect for their peers. To lead others, dealing with emotions around this pandemic is important. Adults should continue to reach out to their mentees to encourage them and to let them know they are supported. Strathmann (2020) stated that the definition of leadership speaks to its core sentiment and tells that they do not need a fancy title to be considered a leader. Great leaders must have exceptional communication skills, which enables them to share their vision of the future with others. In fact, Harvard experts say adopting a growth mindset is crucial to becoming an effective leader. Poltorak (2020) stated that being a student leader on campus is difficult, especially when faced with unexpected events such as COVID-19. Many students can learn a lot from their experiences as leaders, but it is important to remember the things above in order to have a balance between the position and other obligations.

O'Scanaill (2021) stated that the teacher or adult typically fills the leadership role in the classroom. As educators guide students to make decisions for themselves and develop their overall intellect and self-confidence, some leeway has to be made for students to step into leadership roles. Allowing students to work together automatically enables students to assign themselves roles within the group. One or more students will often take the lead role without realizing it. This allows students to gain confidence within group activities while understanding the role they tend to be most comfortable in. Risk-taking is a hard task even for adults to accomplish and manage. If students understand that success will not come easily the first time they try, they are usually more willing to make mistakes, take risks, and excel in any environment. Some students are not as willing or excited about leadership in their everyday lives. Student leadership is incredibly important for a student's development, especially when entering the real world. Taking ownership of school- or work-related tasks in their own lives can help them meet great potential in the future.

Hernando-Malipot (2021) wrote that two Filipino students from a Makati-based school represented the Philippines during the Asia Student Leadership Conference 2021 hosted by Smile Asia Organization in Singapore. The Asia Student Leadership Conference is an annual event giving students a platform to receive training from notable individuals across the globe to enhance intercultural awareness, strengthen their leadership skills and character, and become creators of change. This two-day conference consists of student leaders to learn about the core values of service, leadership, education, and volunteerism. With the theme *Lux Brumalis*, which means "The Light of Winter," the conference shed light on the universal experiences and changes brought about by the pandemic. Through this event, Smile Asia hopes to facilitate conversations about the personal volunteering experiences of international and local students to inspire a new generation of leaders who can bring light to others. The participation of the students is part of iACADEMY's efforts to encourage them to take an active role in volunteering and leading for change. This initiative is spearheaded by the Office of Students Affairs and Services (OSAS), which seeks opportunities to engage students with both local and international organizations.

On the one hand, Medina (2021) wrote that the benefits of being a student leader outweigh any time that may be "wasted" on it by practicing communication skills. He defines student leaders loosely, from class beadies to student government leaders. One has to be readily able to channel his or her ideas to the rest of the team and learn to listen. Listening to people comes hand-in-hand with engaging in dialogue. No matter how high you get in a hierarchy, you still ought to listen to people and allow them to exercise their capabilities as well. Hard skills are also one of the many things to consider - in other student organizations, students plan all their events. There are many things to consider—the logistics, documentation, programs, sponsors, partnerships, creatives, finances, and more. Despite being extremely busy with academics, exerting remarkable dedication and professionalism in all endeavors is fulfilling. Try joining the student-led organization, and you will learn so much in life; even if you discover that student leadership might not be your thing, sometimes a "rejection" is simply a redirection to something greater, and there's nothing to lose by simply trying it out.

Whereas Siscar and Ojales (2021) researched Developing Leadership Potentials of Supreme Pupil Government in Public Elementary Schools. The Student Pupil Government (SPG) implements relevant programs, projects, and activities in Philippine schools. This study assessed the performance of SPG officers in Area 3, Division of Batangas to enhance their leadership potential. This study covered the assessment of how SPG officers performed the assigned duties along with planning, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation. Likewise, this also dealt with the SPG advisers' mentoring activities and even described SPG officers' leadership qualities and potentials. Moreover, the issues and challenges encountered that significantly impact SPG officers' leadership were also identified. The descriptive research method was utilized in the study, with a questionnaire as the main data-gathering instrument. Interviews and focus group discussions were conducted to enrich the findings of the study. Respondents included 148 school heads and 148 SPG advisers from Area III, Division of Batangas Province. Results from the findings revealed that the SPG officers need to improve their skills in planning activities conducted in schools. Also, SPG advisers should continue working with SPG officers to ensure effective implementation and coordination among

school officials and the student body. Leadership qualities and potential are remarkable among SPG officers. Concerns about administrative support and cooperation are the topmost issues and challenges that affect SPG officers' leadership. The proposed plan of activities may be relevant resources for enhancing SPG officers' competencies and performance

Theoretical Underpinnings

This study is anchored to Perkins' (2007) Theory of Difficulty. Most educational researchers, school administrators, and experienced teachers develop what might be called theories of difficulty. A strong theory of difficulty identifies learners' characteristic trouble spots for a particular area of instruction and includes some causal analysis of why they occur toward improved teaching and learning. The literature on learning and development offers numerous ways of understanding conceptual difficulties, as well as recognizing problems of ritualized knowledge, inert knowledge, knowledge to foreign for learners to engage it readily, and tacit knowledge, the partly unconscious nature of which poses learning challenges. In several studies, a strong theory of difficulty has led to improved learning. In everyday teaching, teachers' responses to recurrent difficulties may fall short. One uncommon reaction is to blame the learners' weaknesses and simply keep teaching in the same way. Another better reaction is to 'teach harder', lavishing more time and attention on characteristic difficulties without any causal analysis of what makes them problematic. The most effective is to 'teach smarter' based on a causal analysis refined through experience. The construction of informal theories of difficulty is an important part of the craft of teaching. His theory was relevant to the study because it explains how student leaders build what are known as difficult or challenging ideas. The theory of difficulty is most significant in determining difficulties encountered by student leaders in the new normal.

Objectives

This study aimed to determine the level of difficulties encountered by student leaders in the new normal in one of the medium-sized Divisions in Region III. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions: 1) the level of difficulties encountered by student leaders in the new normal according to the area of knowledge, ability and attitude; 2) the level of difficulties encountered by the Student Leaders in the new normal when grouped according to the aforementioned variables; and 3) the significant difference in the level of difficulties encountered by the respondents when grouped according to the aforementioned variables.

Methodology

This section presents the discussion of the research methodology used, the subjects and respondents of the study, the research instruments used, the validity and reliability of the instruments, the procedure for data gathering, and the statistical tools and procedure for data analysis.

Research Design

This study employed the descriptive research design to determine the level of difficulties encountered by student leaders in the new normal in one of the medium-sized Divisions in Region III. Descriptive research examines a person's current situation and is commonly utilized in fields such as education, nutrition, epidemiology, and behavioral sciences. Its worth is based on the idea that by observation, analysis, and description, issues can be solved and practices improved. The survey, which comprises questionnaires, personal interviews, phone surveys, and normative surveys, is the most used descriptive research approach (Waiters, 2019). This research design is considered appropriate for this particular study because its purpose is to discover student leaders' difficulties in the new normal. This study's nature is to assess the condition of things in their present state. Likewise, it delves into the relationship among variables considered in the study and the influence of one variable on another.

Study Respondents

The respondents of the study are ninety-one (91) Supreme Student Government Officers in the Schools Division Office of Zambales. Purposive sampling was used in this study. Purposive sampling, also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling, is a form of non-probability sampling in which researchers rely on their own judgment when choosing members of the population to participate in their surveys (Alchemer, 2021).

Instruments

This study used a self-made questionnaire to gather the data. The questionnaire is divided into 2 parts: Part 1 contains queries on respondents' profiles such as age, sex, school category, and average monthly income. Part 2 is the questionnaire, which includes items focused on the difficulties encountered by student leaders in the following areas in the new normal. This study utilized the Likert Scale rating with 5 as always, 4 as often, 3 as sometimes, 2 as rarely, and 1 as almost never. The survey instruments were subjected to validity and reliability test. The validity rating was 4.81, interpreted as "Excellent," which means that the instruments used in this study were valid and the

reliability index was 0.967, interpreted as "Excellent," which means that the questionnaire developed by the researcher is highly reliable.

Data Gathering Procedure

For the smoother conduct of the study, the researcher sought permission from the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) and School Heads through the Public Schools District Supervisor (PSDS) to undertake the study. A letter request was furnished to the SDS in the Schools Division Office of Zambales for reliability testing of the research instrument. Upon approval, the researcher scheduled the administration of the questionnaire in order to avoid inconvenience and unpreparedness on the part of the respondents. During the administration of the questionnaire, since face-to-face transactions are being discouraged because of the current health crisis, the researcher utilized the Google Online Survey Form to administer the survey questionnaire. The researcher will also give proper instructions and will clearly explain the objectives of the study as well as the terms and items contained in the instruments so that respondents will fully understand their tasks of answering the tests via call, text, email, and Facebook messenger whichever is convenient to the respondents. The test scores and other data were then retrieved, tallied, tabulated, and interpreted.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1 used the descriptive analytical scheme and means to determine the level of difficulties encountered by the respondents in the new normal in terms of knowledge, ability, and attitude.

Objective no. 2 used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the level of difficulties encountered by the respondents when grouped according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective No.3 used the comparative analytical scheme and m Mann-Whitney U test to determine the significant difference in the level of difficulties encountered by the respondents when grouped according to the aforementioned variables.

Ethical Consideration

Participants' personal demographic information results were collected and were noted in the data capturing sheet. Informed consent via verbal communication was elicited with the respondents. They read and understood the provided information and can ask questions. Moreover, their participation was voluntary, and they were free to withdraw without giving any reasons. The respondents were assured that there would be no risks of harm will experience before, during, or after participating in the research. The data and information used in the study were treated with strict confidentiality. No statement regarding the participant's identity was disclosed unnecessarily in this study. After the data gathering, since there was no need, debriefing was not done by the researcher anymore, as cited in the Data Privacy Act.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data gathered to carry out the objectives of this study. All these were made possible by following certain appropriate procedures so as to give the exact data and solution to each specific problem.

Table 1

Level of Difficulties Encountered by Student Leaders in the New Normal According to Knowledge

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a student leader, I encounter difficulties in ...</i>		
1. Planning and creating the General Plan of Action in the new normal education.	3.75	High Level
2. Outsourcing ideas from other student leaders.	3.69	High Level
3. Designing a strategy to encourage students to participate in youth formation programs, projects, and activities in the new normal.	3.70	High Level
4. Preparing infographics, videos, and slide presentations for each activity adaptive to the new normal.	3.44	Moderate Level
5. Delegating the tasks to each member for effective activity delivery.	3.69	High Level
6. Setting manageable goals to achieve in the new normal.	3.62	High Level
7. Accelerating decision-making to make quick and reliable decisions.	3.60	High Level
8. Sharing ideas with the team.	3.64	High Level
9. Developing approaches to solve various issues among student leaders during the new normal education.	3.66	High Level

10. Understanding different protocols in implementing the other programs, projects, and activities aligns with DepEd's core values in the new normal.	3.65	High Level
Overall Mean	3.64	High Level

According to knowledge, the data presented the level of difficulties encountered by student leaders in the new normal. As a whole, the table showed that there was a high level of difficulty with an overall mean score of 3.64%. Meanwhile, the data revealed that item no. 4, or preparing infographics, videos, and slide presentations for each activity adaptive to the new normal, obtained a mean of 3.44% or moderate difficulty level. Item no. 1, or the Planning and Creating the General Plan of Action in the new normal education, got the highest mean of 3.75% or a high level of difficulty. This result implied that student leaders have difficulty discussing and facilitating the establishment of a plan of action in the new normal of education.

Moreover, this result also conforms to the discussion of Lituañas et al. (2021) that the COVID-19 pandemic has impacted student councils in terms of their structure and processes, formation programs, and resource generation capacity. Furthermore, Asghar et al. (2021) concluded that the education shift to virtual learning environments during the COVID-19 pandemic has been overwhelming for students, who rely heavily on the contextual application of knowledge.

Table 2
Level of Difficulties Encountered by Student Leaders in the New Normal According to Ability

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a student leader, I encounter difficulties in ...</i>		
1. Using an accessible platform for convenience and smooth delivery of the different programs, projects, and activities in the new normal.	3.69	High Level
2. Simplifying concepts during asynchronous implementation of the youth formation programs, projects, and activities.	3.52	High Level
3. Ensuring students' learning capacity by age, considering the Screen Time Guidelines in the new normal education.	3.63	High Level
4. Using everyday language to all students in presenting concepts and ideas.	3.53	High Level
5. Addressing questions and concerns of the students in each activity.	3.64	High Level
6. Monitoring and evaluating each program, project, or activity in the new normal.	3.68	High Level
7. Providing Technical Assistance to ensure the delivery of programs and projects in the new normal.	3.66	High Level
8. Providing analogy and constructive feedback on each program, project, or activity.	3.49	High Level
9. Training in digital technology to match online activities in the new normal.	3.41	Moderate Level
10. Providing starter kit materials to understand and practice the activity.	3.45	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.57	High Level

The table disclosed the results of the level of difficulties encountered by student leaders in the new normal according to ability. The data revealed that the level of problems faced by student leaders according to ability was high level, with an overall mean score of 3.57%. In addition, the results presented a moderate level of difficulty in item no. 9 or the training in digital technology to match online activities in the new normal with a mean score of 3.41%. Item no. 1, or using an accessible platform for convenience and smooth delivery of the different programs, projects, and activities in the new normal, obtained a mean score of 3.69%, translating to a high difficulty level. This result implied that the respondents' ability to utilize various platforms to smoothly deliver the different programs, projects, and activities online faced a big challenge. This could be attributed to geographical location wherein the internet is poor or unstable. Likewise, some are not that literate in using technology. This result affirmed Northouse (2019), who emphasized that adaptive work requires determining what currently requires change while rethinking how organizations will adapt and thrive in a new environment.

Table 3
Level of Difficulties Encountered by Student Leaders in the New Normal According to Attitude

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a student leader, I encounter difficulties in ...</i>		
1. Upholding the DepEd Core Values in the new normal.	3.47	Moderate Level
2. Prioritizing honesty at all times.	3.57	High Level
3. Doing the best that I can to ensure the well-being of other students in the new normal education.	3.64	High Level
4. Managing my time and energy wisely in the new normal.	3.73	High Level

5. Making a commitment to self-improvement.	3.54	High Level
6. Showing willingness to embrace opportunities in the new normal.	3.51	High Level
7. Adapting to change and even pushing change forward.	3.42	Moderate Level
8. Rewarding and recognizing the good action of the team.	3.47	Moderate Level
9. Valuing the interconnectedness of the team.	3.54	High Level
10. Taking advantage of the situation into opportunity in the new normal.	3.46	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.53	High Level

The table exhibited the results of the level of difficulties encountered by student leaders in the new normal according to attitude. There was a high level of difficulty, with an overall mean score of 3.53%. Additionally, the data showed that the student leaders encountered moderate difficulty in item no. 7 or adapting to change and even pushing change forward with a mean score of 3.42%. On the other hand, item no. 4, or managing their time and energy wisely in the new normal, obtained a mean score of 3.73%, or a high level of difficulty. This outcome inferred that the student leaders were becoming discomposed due to the changes brought by the pandemic. Managing time was difficult for them, possibly because of the bulk of work to be finished on time. According to Sopon (2017), improving time management among undergraduates is still a challenge, even though universities provide a wealth of information on time management skills on their websites.

Table 4

Level of Difficulties Encountered by Student Leaders in the New Normal According to Knowledge in terms of age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a student leader, I encounter difficulties in ...</i>				
1. Planning and creating the General Plan of Action in the new normal education.	3.76	High Level	3.74	High Level
2. Outsourcing ideas from other student leaders.	3.73	High Level	3.64	High Level
3. Designing a strategy to encourage students to participate in youth formation programs, projects, and activities in the new normal.	3.84	High Level	3.55	High Level
4. Preparing infographics, videos, and slide presentations for each activity adaptive to the new normal.	3.55	High Level	3.31	Moderate Level
5. Delegating the tasks to each member for effective delivery of the activity.	3.96	High Level	3.38	Moderate Level
6. Setting manageable goals to achieve in the new normal.	3.69	High Level	3.52	High Level
7. Accelerating decision-making to make quick and reliable decisions.	3.84	High Level	3.33	Moderate Level
8. Sharing ideas with the team.	3.86	High Level	3.38	Moderate Level
9. Developing approaches to solve various issues arising among student leaders during the new normal education.	3.80	High Level	3.50	High Level
10. Understanding different protocols in implementing the various programs, projects, and activities aligns with DepEd's core values in the new normal.	3.86	High Level	3.40	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.79	High Level	3.48	Moderate Level

The table presented the results of the level of difficulties encountered by student leaders in the new normal according to knowledge in terms of age. Overall, the data showed a high level of difficulty among the younger respondents, with an overall mean of 3.79%. Additionally, the younger and older respondents obtained the lowest mean of 3.55% and 3.31% in item no. 4 or preparing infographics, videos, and slide presentations for each activity adaptive to the new normal. On the other hand, the younger respondents obtained the highest mean of 3.96% in item no. 5 or delegating tasks to each member to effectively deliver the activity. At the same time, the older respondents got the highest mean of 3.74% in item no. 1 or planning and creating the General Plan of Action in the new normal education. Thus, these results implied difficulty in dividing and assigning tasks among the members, and planning the program online was a challenge among the older ones. This finding correlates with Karim and Mitra (2015), who indicate that poor time management is evident among students, which is a big challenge. Likewise, the lack of a plan of action to finish academic work early is added to their challenges.

Table 5

Level of Difficulties Encountered by Student Leaders in the New Normal According to Ability in terms of age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a student leader, I encounter difficulties in ...</i>				
1. Using an accessible platform for convenience and smooth	3.84	High Level	3.52	High Level

delivery of the different programs, projects, and activities in the new normal.

2. Simplifying concepts during asynchronous implementation of the youth formation programs, projects, and activities.	3.61	High Level	3.40	Moderate Level
3. Ensuring students' learning capacity by age, considering the Screen Time Guidelines in the new normal education.	3.71	High Level	3.52	High Level
4. Using common language with all students when presenting concepts and ideas.	3.55	High Level	3.50	High Level
5. Addressing questions and concerns of the students in each activity.	3.71	High Level	3.55	High Level
6. Monitoring and evaluating each program, project, or activity in the new normal.	3.82	High Level	3.52	High Level
7. Providing Technical Assistance to ensure the delivery of programs and projects in the new normal.	3.71	High Level	3.60	High Level
8. Providing analogy and constructive feedback on each program, project, or activity.	3.57	High Level	3.40	Moderate Level
9. Training in digital technology to match online activities in the new normal.	3.57	High Level	3.21	Moderate Level
10. Providing starter kit materials to understand and practice the activity.	3.53	High Level	3.36	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.66	High Level	3.46	Moderate Level

The table above shows the data on the level of difficulties encountered by student leaders in the new normal according to ability in terms of age. Overall, the data showed a high level of difficulty among the younger respondents, with a mean of 3.66%. Moreover, the data showed that younger respondents got the lowest mean of 3.53% in item no. 10 or provided starter kit materials to understand and practice the activity. At the same time, the older respondents obtained the lowest mean of 3.21% in item no. 9 or training in digital technology to match online activities in the new normal. Likewise, the younger respondents got the highest mean of 3.84% in item no. 1 or using an accessible platform for convenience and smooth delivery of the different programs, projects, and activities in the new normal. While the older respondents obtained the highest mean of 3.60% in item no. 7 or providing Technical Assistance to ensure the delivery of programs and projects in the new normal. This means that accessible online platform is a challenge for younger respondents while providing technical assistance to ensure the delivery of programs and projects in the new normal is challenging for older ones. This could be attributed to the following: unstable internet connection, lack of training in ICT, and insufficient devices for younger ones. For older, results could be attributed to the bulk of workloads or inadequate time management. This result conforms to the discussion of Hargreaves (2020). In his research, he discussed that school leaders need to be discerning about the digital products they choose and be careful about striking a balance between technology and pedagogy in their schools.

Table 6

Level of Difficulties Encountered by Student Leaders in the New Normal According to Attitude in terms of age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a student leader, I encounter difficulties in ...</i>				
1. Upholding the DepEd Core Values in the new normal.	3.65	High Level	3.26	Moderate Level
2. Prioritizing honesty at all times.	3.84	High Level	3.26	Moderate Level
3. Doing the best that I can to ensure the well-being of other students in the new normal education.	3.84	High Level	3.40	Moderate Level
4. Managing my time and energy wisely in the new normal.	3.96	High Level	3.45	Moderate Level
5. Making a commitment to self-improvement.	3.86	High Level	3.17	Moderate Level
6. Showing willingness to embrace opportunities in the new normal.	3.82	High Level	3.14	Moderate Level
7. Adapting to change and even pushing change forward.	3.65	High Level	3.14	Moderate Level
8. Rewarding and recognizing the good action of the team.	3.63	High Level	3.29	Moderate Level
9. Valuing the interconnectedness of the team.	3.76	High Level	3.29	Moderate Level

10. Taking advantage of the situation into opportunity in the new normal.	3.80	High Level	3.07	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.78	High Level	3.25	Moderate Level

The table showed the results of the level of difficulties encountered by student leaders in the new normal according to attitude in terms of age. The older respondents obtained a moderate level of difficulty, with an overall mean of 3.25% or a moderate level, and the younger respondents got 3.78% or a high level. In light of the results, the older respondents got the lowest mean of 3.07% or moderate level in item no. 10 or taking advantage of the situation into opportunity in the new normal. Meanwhile, the younger respondents obtained the lowest mean of 3.63% or higher level in item no. 8 or rewarding and recognizing the excellent action of the team. On the other hand, the older respondents obtained the highest mean of 3.45% or moderate level. Likewise, the younger respondents got the highest mean of 3.96% or high level both in item no. 4 or managing their time and energy wisely in the new normal. These results inferred that whether young or old, respondents encountered difficulties managing online meetings and ensuring safety at home. This finding affirms the conclusion of Alvarez et al. (2021). Their study highlighted that the pandemic created many educational problems that require special skills, such as communication, digital knowledge, empathy, and interaction. Similarly, Van Wyk (2016) found that 47.9% of university students in South Africa drop out of school before their program ends. Due to their lack of academic preparation and self-discipline, many people struggled with time management.

Table 7

Level of Difficulties Encountered by Student Leaders in the New Normal According to Knowledge in Terms of Sex

Items	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a student leader, I encounter difficulties in ...</i>				
1. Planning and creating the General Plan of Action in the new normal education.	3.83	High Level	3.72	High Level
2. Outsourcing ideas from other student leaders.	3.39	Moderate Level	3.79	High Level
3. Designing a strategy to encourage students to participate in youth formation programs, projects, and activities in the new normal.	3.52	High Level	3.76	High Level
4. Preparing infographics, videos, and slide presentations for each activity adaptive to the new normal.	3.48	Moderate Level	3.43	Moderate Level
5. Delegating the tasks to each member for effective activity delivery.	3.70	High Level	3.69	High Level
6. Setting manageable goals to achieve in the new normal.	3.61	High Level	3.62	High Level
7. Accelerating decision-making to make quick and reliable decisions.	3.74	High Level	3.56	High Level
8. Sharing ideas with the team.	3.65	High Level	3.63	High Level
9. Developing approaches to solve various issues arising among student leaders during the new normal education.	3.43	Moderate Level	3.74	High Level
10. Understanding different protocols in implementing the various programs, projects, and activities aligns with DepEd's core values in the new normal.	3.61	High Level	3.66	High Level
Overall Mean	3.60	High Level	3.66	High Level

The table presented the results of the level of difficulties encountered by student leaders in the new normal according to knowledge in terms of sex. Overall, the data showed a high level of difficulty for female respondents, with an overall mean of 3.66%. Moreover, the data in each item showed that the male respondents got the lowest mean score of 3.39% or moderate level in item no. 2 or outsourcing ideas from other student leaders. Also, the female respondents got the lowest mean score of 3.43% or moderate level in item no. 4 or preparing infographics, videos, and slide presentations for each activity adaptive to the new normal. Further, the male respondents attained the highest mean score of 3.83% or high level in item no. 1 or planning and creating the General Plan of Action in the new normal education. Meanwhile, the female respondents got the highest mean score of 3.79% in item no. 2 or outsourcing ideas from other student leaders. These results explained that there was a high difficulty for male respondents to make and discuss a plan of action online, while female respondents struggled to solicit and get ideas from other student leaders. This outcome affirms Bird et al. (2020) emphasized that the uncertainty of the COVID-19 pandemic is frightening and daunting. However, we have a new opportunity to ask timely questions to understand differences in risk and outcome, including how women and men differ.

Table 8

Level of Difficulties Encountered by Student Leaders in the New Normal According to Ability in terms of Sex

Items	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a student leader, I encounter difficulties in ...</i>				
1. Using an accessible platform for convenience and smooth delivery of the different programs, projects, and activities in the new normal.	3.70	High Level	3.69	High Level
2. Simplifying concepts during asynchronous implementation of the youth formation programs, projects, and activities.	3.52	High Level	3.51	High Level
3. Ensuring students' learning capacity by age, considering the Screen Time Guidelines in the new normal education.	3.70	High Level	3.60	High Level
4. Using common language to all students in presenting concepts and ideas.	3.70	High Level	3.47	Moderate Level
5. Addressing questions and concerns of the students in each activity.	3.83	High Level	3.57	High Level
6. Monitoring and evaluating each program, project, or activity in the new normal.	3.61	High Level	3.71	High Level
7. Providing Technical Assistance to ensure the delivery of programs and projects in the new normal.	3.70	High Level	3.65	High Level
8. Providing analogy and constructive feedback on each program, project, or activity.	3.48	Moderate Level	3.50	High Level
9. Training in digital technology to match online activities in the new normal.	3.35	Moderate Level	3.43	Moderate Level
10. Providing starter kit materials to understand and practice the activity.	3.61	High Level	3.40	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.62	High Level	3.55	High Level

The table showed the results of the level of difficulties encountered by student leaders according to ability when they were grouped according to Sex. When taken as a whole, the data presented a high level of difficulty, with an overall mean score of 3.62% for male and 3.55% for female respondents, respectively. In addition, the details showed that the male respondents got the lowest mean of 3.35% or moderate level in item no. 9 or training in digital technology to match online activities in the new normal, while the female respondents got the lowest mean score of 3.40% or moderate level in item no. 10 or providing starter kit materials to understand and practice the activity. Moreover, the male respondents obtained the highest mean of 3.83% or high level in item no. 5 or addressing questions and concerns of the students in each activity, and the female respondents got the highest mean score of 3.71% or high level in item no. 6 or monitoring and evaluating of each program, project, or activity in the new normal. These outcomes revealed that male respondents were challenged in their ability to address different queries and concerns of the students through online activities, and female respondents could hardly do monitoring and evaluation online. This result conforms with Heifetz & Linsk (2017), who emphasized that leaders must demonstrate an adaptive mindset to lead effectively through the change). Moreover, the study of Dykstra-Lathrop (2022) also affirms that the biggest challenge was being an instructional leader in the unfamiliar milieu of online teaching and learning.

Table 9

Level of Difficulties Encountered by Student Leaders in the New Normal According to Attitude in terms of Sex

Items	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a student leader, I encounter difficulties in ...</i>				
1. Upholding the DepEd Core Values in the new normal.	3.43	Moderate Level	3.49	Moderate Level
2. Prioritizing honesty at all times.	3.43	Moderate Level	3.62	High Level
3. Doing the best I can to ensure other students' well-being in the new normal education.	3.39	Moderate Level	3.72	High Level
4. Managing my time and energy wisely in the new normal.	3.39	Moderate Level	3.84	High Level
5. Making a commitment to self-improvement.	3.35	Moderate Level	3.60	High Level
6. Showing willingness to embrace opportunities in the new normal.	3.35	Moderate Level	3.56	High Level
7. Adapting to change and even pushing change forward.	3.39	Moderate Level	3.43	Moderate Level
8. Rewarding and recognizing the good action of the team.	3.30	Moderate Level	3.53	High Level

9. Valuing the interconnectedness of the team.	3.48	Moderate Level	3.56	High Level
10. Taking advantage of the situation into opportunity in the new normal.	3.43	Moderate Level	3.47	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.40	Moderate Level	3.58	High Level

The table revealed the results of the level of difficulties encountered by student leaders in the new normal according to attitude in terms of Sex. When taken as a whole, male respondents obtained an overall mean score of 3.40% or moderate difficulty level. Likewise, female respondents got an overall mean score of 3.58% or a high level of difficulty. Additionally, the data presented that the male respondents obtained the lowest mean of 3.30% or moderate level in item no. 8 or rewarding and recognizing the excellent action of the team, and the female respondents got the lowest mean of 3.43% or moderate level in item no. 7 or adapting to change and even pushing change forward. On the other hand, the male respondents got the highest mean score of 3.48% or moderate level in item no. 9 or valuing the interconnectedness of the team, while the female respondents got the highest mean of 3.84% or high level in item no.4 or managing their time and energy wisely in the new normal. Further, male respondents' results showed moderate difficulty in maintaining connectedness among student leaders online. Also, female respondents indicated a high level of difficulty in terms of managing their time and the energy they need online. Subsequently, this finding was unlikely to agree with Korlat et al. (2021). He concluded that it had been found that boys describe themselves with computers significantly more often than girls. Moreover, it also affirms the study of Drabowicz (2014), whose findings explained that boys' computer use for education and entertainment is more frequent.

Table 10
Level of Difficulties Encountered by Student Leaders in the New Normal According to the Area Knowledge According to School Category

Items	Small		Medium		Large/Mega	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a student leader, I encounter difficulties in ...</i>						
1. Planning and creating the General Plan of Action in the new normal education.	3.55	High Level	3.87	High Level	3.78	High Level
2. Outsourcing ideas from other student leaders.	3.45	Moderate Level	3.74	High Level	3.91	High Level
3. Designing a strategy to encourage students to participate in youth formation programs, projects, and activities in the new normal.	3.41	Moderate Level	3.85	High Level	3.83	High Level
4. Preparing infographics, videos, and slide presentations for each activity adaptive to the new normal.	3.28	Moderate Level	3.54	High Level	3.48	Moderate Level
5. Delegating the tasks to each member for effective delivery of the activity.	3.41	Moderate Level	3.87	High Level	3.74	High Level
6. Setting manageable goals to achieve in the new normal.	3.24	Moderate Level	3.90	High Level	3.61	High Level
7. Accelerating decision-making to make quick and reliable decisions.	3.31	Moderate Level	3.79	High Level	3.65	High Level
8. Sharing ideas with the team.	3.21	Moderate Level	3.90	High Level	3.74	High Level
9. Developing approaches to solve various issues arising among student leaders during the new normal education.	3.24	Moderate Level	3.92	High Level	3.74	High Level
10. Understanding different protocols in implementing the various programs, projects, and activities aligns with DepEd's core values in the new normal.	3.21	Moderate Level	3.85	High Level	3.87	High Level
Overall Mean	3.33	Moderate Level	3.82	High Level	3.73	High Level

The table presented the results of the level of difficulties encountered by student leaders in terms of knowledge when grouped according to school category. The small schools obtained an overall mean score of 3.33% or moderate level, the medium schools obtained an overall mean score of 3.82% or high level, and the large/mega schools obtained an overall mean score of 3.73% or a high level of difficulty. Moreover, the details revealed that the small schools got the lowest mean of 3.21% or moderate level in item no. 8 or sharing ideas to the team, identical to item no. 10 or understanding different protocols in implementing the various programs, projects, and activities align in DepEd core values in the new normal. Likewise, the medium and large/mega schools got the lowest mean of 3.54% or high level and 3.48% or moderate level, respectively, in item no. 4 or preparing infographics, videos, and slide presentations for each activity adaptive to the new normal. On the contrary, the small schools got the highest mean of 3.55% or a high level in item no. 1, or planning and creating the General Plan of Action in the new normal education. Meanwhile, the medium schools obtained the highest mean of 3.92% or a high level in item no. 9 or developing approaches to solve various issues arising among student leaders during the new normal education. The large/mega schools got the highest mean of 3.91% or a high level in item no. 2 or outsourcing ideas from other student leaders.

Further, these results implied that regardless of the school category, the difficulty of student leaders in planning, developing approaches and strategies, and soliciting ideas was prevailing. Thus, this result conforms to Jefferies's (2017) study, he emphasized that the path forward is for school leaders to learn their way through these challenges and lean on their colleagues to embrace different approaches than previously undertaken. Also, in the study of Northouse (2019), he supported that adaptive work requires determining what currently requires change while rethinking how organizations will adapt and thrive in a new environment.

Table 11

Level of Difficulties Encountered by Student Leaders in the New Normal According to Ability in terms of School Category

Items	Small		Medium		Large/Mega	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a student leader, I encounter difficulties in ...</i>						
1. Using an accessible platform for convenience and smooth delivery of the different programs, projects, and activities in the new normal.	3.34	Moderate Level	3.90	High Level	3.78	High Level
2. Simplifying concepts during asynchronous implementation of the youth formation programs, projects, and activities.	3.38	Moderate Level	3.59	High Level	3.57	High Level
3. Ensuring students' learning capacity in consideration of the Screen Time Guidelines by Age in the new normal education.	3.24	Moderate Level	3.69	High Level	4.00	High Level
4. Using common language to all students in presenting concepts and ideas.	3.17	Moderate Level	3.62	High Level	3.83	High Level
5. Addressing questions and concerns of the students in each activity.	3.31	Moderate Level	3.64	High Level	4.04	High Level
6. Monitoring and evaluating of each program, project, or activity in the new normal.	3.41	Moderate Level	3.69	High Level	4.00	High Level
7. Providing Technical Assistance to ensure the delivery of programs and projects in the new normal.	3.34	Moderate Level	3.67	High Level	4.04	High Level
8. Providing analogy and constructive feedback on each program, project, or activity.	3.28	Moderate Level	3.54	High Level	3.70	High Level
9. Training in digital technology to match online activities in the new normal.	3.14	Moderate Level	3.56	High Level	3.48	Moderate Level
10. Providing starter kit materials to understand and practice the activity.	3.31	Moderate Level	3.64	High Level	3.30	Moderate Level

Overall Mean	3.29	Moderate Level	3.65	High Level	3.77	High Level
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The table showed the level of difficulties encountered by student leaders according to ability when grouped according to school category. As a whole, the small schools got an overall mean score of 3.29% or a moderate level, and the medium schools obtained an overall mean score of 3.65% or a high level. Moreover, the large/mega schools got an overall mean score of 3.77% or a high level of difficulty. Additionally, the data revealed that the small schools got the lowest mean of 3.14% or moderate level in item no. 9 or training in digital technology to match online activities in the new normal. The medium schools got the lowest mean of 3.54% or high level in item no. 8, providing analogy and constructive feedback on each program, project, or activity. The large/mega schools obtained the lowest mean of 3.30% or moderate level in item no. 10 or providing starter kit materials to understand and practice the activity. On the other hand, the small schools got the highest mean of 3.41% or moderate level in item no. 6 or monitoring and evaluating of each program, project, or activity in the new normal. The medium schools got the highest mean of 3.90% or high level in item no. 1 or using an accessible platform for convenience and smooth delivery of the different programs, projects, and activities in the new normal. The large/mega schools obtained the highest mean of 4.04% in both items no. 5 or addressing questions and concerns of the students in each activity and item no. 7 or providing Technical Assistance to ensure the delivery of programs and projects in the new normal. These results inferred that schools vary in their challenges regarding utilizing online platforms. Further, respondents from small schools experienced difficulty in the ability to conduct monitoring and evaluation of the different programs, while those from medium schools were challenged to have the ability to create mediums to address students' concerns and provide assistance.

Further, these findings affirm the conclusions of Raelin (2016) that by distributing leadership responsibilities, school leaders can lay the groundwork for collaboration, deepen relationships, and foster ownership and innovation through a process of collective problem-solving. Furthermore, Kuntz et al. (2017) also confirm in their findings that adaptive leaders understand how trust, flexibility, and autonomy encourage organic expertise to flourish, which can motivate others to take creative approaches in tackling unforeseen challenges and needs as they arise.

Table 12

Level of Difficulties Encountered by Student Leaders in the New Normal According to Attitude in terms of School Category

Items	Small		Medium		Large/Mega	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a student leader, I encounter difficulties in ...</i>						
1. Upholding the DepEd Core Values in the new normal.	3.48	Moderate Level	3.41	Moderate Level	3.57	High Level
2. Prioritizing honesty at all times.	3.31	Moderate Level	3.62	High Level	3.83	High Level
3. Doing the best that I can to ensure the well-being of other students in the new normal education.	3.24	Moderate Level	3.72	High Level	4.00	High Level
4. Managing my time and energy wisely in the new normal.	3.48	Moderate Level	3.74	High Level	4.00	High Level
5. Making a commitment to self-improvement.	3.34	Moderate Level	3.54	High Level	3.78	High Level
6. Showing willingness to embrace opportunities in the new normal.	3.21	Moderate Level	3.51	High Level	3.87	High Level
7. Adapting to change and even pushing change forward.	3.28	Moderate Level	3.38	Moderate Level	3.65	High Level
8. Rewarding and recognizing the excellent action of the team.	3.28	Moderate Level	3.46	Moderate Level	3.74	High Level
9. Valuing the interconnectedness of the team.	3.31	Moderate Level	3.44	Moderate Level	4.00	High Level
10. Taking advantage of the situation into opportunity in the new normal.	3.10	Moderate Level	3.36	Moderate Level	4.09	High Level
Overall Mean	3.30	Moderate Level	3.52	High Level	3.85	High Level

This table presented the results of the level of difficulties encountered by student leaders according to attitude when grouped in terms of school category. As a whole, the data shows that the small schools obtained an overall mean score of 3.30% or a moderate level, the medium schools got an overall mean score of 3.52% or a high level, while the large/mega schools obtained an overall mean score of 3.85% or a high level of difficulty. Moreover, the respondents from small schools and medium schools obtained the lowest mean scores of 3.10% and 3.36% or moderate level, respectively, in item no. 10 or taking advantage of the situation into opportunity in the new normal, while the respondents from the large/mega schools got the lowest mean score of 3.57% or high level in item no. 1 or upholding the DepEd Core Values in the new normal. On the other hand, the small schools attained the highest mean score of 3.48% or moderate levels in both item no. 1, or upholding the DepEd Core Values in the new normal, and item no. 4, or managing their time and energy wisely in the new normal. At the same time, the respondents from medium schools got the highest mean score of 3.74% or a high level in item no. 4 or managing their time and energy wisely in the new normal. The respondents from the large/mega schools got the highest mean score of 4.09% or high level in item no. 10 or taking advantage of the situation into opportunity in the new normal. Given these data, the results implied moderate difficulty among the respondents in small schools regarding their approach to upholding the DepEd's core values and keeping interactive online sessions. Likewise, medium and large/mega schools have difficulty maximizing potential online.

Table 13

Level of Difficulties Encountered by Student Leaders in the New Normal According to Knowledge in terms of Average Family Monthly Income

Items	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a student leader, I encounter difficulties in ...</i>				
1. Planning and creating the General Plan of Action in the new normal education.	3.67	High Level	3.83	High Level
2. Outsourcing ideas from other student leaders.	3.76	High Level	3.63	High Level
3. Designing a strategy to encourage students to participate in youth formation programs, projects, and activities in the new normal.	3.60	High Level	3.80	High Level
4. Preparing infographics, videos, and slide presentations for each activity adaptive to the new normal.	3.42	Moderate Level	3.46	Moderate Level
5. Delegating the tasks to each member for effective activity delivery.	3.56	High Level	3.83	High Level
6. Setting manageable goals to achieve in the new normal.	3.73	High Level	3.50	High Level
7. Accelerating decision-making to make quick and reliable decisions.	3.62	High Level	3.59	High Level
8. Sharing ideas with the team.	3.64	High Level	3.63	High Level
9. Developing approaches to solve various issues arising among student leaders during the new normal education.	3.64	High Level	3.67	High Level
10. Understanding different protocols in implementing the various programs, projects, and activities aligns with DepEd's core values in the new normal.	3.69	High Level	3.61	High Level
Overall Mean	3.63	High Level	3.65	High Level

The table presented the results of the level of difficulties encountered by student leaders according to knowledge when grouped in terms of monthly family income. The data showed that the respondents from a low-income family obtained an overall mean of 3.63%, while respondents from a high-income family got an overall mean of 3.65% or both with a high level of difficulty. In addition, the data revealed that the respondents from low-income families got the lowest mean of 3.42% or moderate level in item no. 4, same with the high-income family, which attained the lowest mean of 3.46% or preparing infographics, videos, and slide presentations for each activity adaptive to the new normal. In contrast, the respondents from low-income families obtained the highest mean of 3.76% or high level in item no. 2 or outsourcing ideas from other student leaders, while the respondents from high-income families got the highest mean of 3.83% or high level in both items no. 1 or planning and creating the General Plan of Action in the new normal education and item no. 5 or delegating of task to each member for effective delivery of the activity. Further, these results inferred that respondents from low-income families struggle to get ideas online, while those from high-income families do not know how to delegate tasks. Furthermore, these findings affirm the conclusion of Hammond (2020) that high-poverty districts reported that a lack of basic technology was a 'major' problem. Moreover, in his study, Wilson (2020) emphasized that school leaders must quickly build relevant knowledge and skills to cope, adapt, and ultimately lead in the pandemic and other times of rapid change.

Table 14

Level of Difficulties Encountered by Student Leaders in the New Normal According to Ability in terms of Average Family Monthly Income

Items	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a student leader, I encounter difficulties in ...</i>				
1. Using an accessible platform for convenience and smooth delivery of the different programs, projects, and activities in the new normal.	3.67	High Level	3.72	High Level
2. Simplifying concepts during asynchronous implementation of the youth formation programs, projects, and activities.	3.38	Moderate Level	3.65	High Level
3. Ensuring students' learning capacity by age, considering the Screen Time Guidelines in the new normal education.	3.51	High Level	3.74	High Level
4. Using common language to all students in presenting concepts and ideas.	3.38	Moderate Level	3.67	High Level
5. Addressing questions and concerns of the students in each activity.	3.51	High Level	3.76	High Level
6. Monitoring and evaluating each program, project, or activity in the new normal.	3.56	High Level	3.80	High Level
7. Providing Technical Assistance to ensure the delivery of programs and projects in the new normal.	3.49	Moderate Level	3.83	High Level
8. Providing analogy and constructive feedback on each program, project, or activity.	3.42	Moderate Level	3.57	High Level
9. Training in digital technology to match online activities in the new normal.	3.13	Moderate Level	3.67	High Level
10. Providing starter kit materials to understand and practice the activity.	3.40	Moderate Level	3.50	High Level
Overall Mean	3.44	Moderate Level	3.69	High Level

The table above revealed the results of the level of difficulties encountered by student leaders according to area ability when grouped in terms of average monthly family income. The data presented that the low-income family respondents obtained an overall mean score of 3.44% or moderate difficulty level. Likewise, respondents from high-income families got an overall mean score of 3.69% or a high level of difficulty. Moreover, the details showed that the respondents from low-income families obtained the lowest mean of 3.13% or moderate level in item no. 9 or training in digital technology to match online activities in the new normal, and those from the high-income families obtained the lowest mean of 3.50% or high level in item no. 10 or providing starter kit materials to understand and practice the activity. On the other hand, the respondents from low-income families achieved the highest mean of 3.67% or high level in item no. 1 or using an accessible platform for convenience and smooth delivery of the new normal's different programs, projects, and activities. Likewise, those in high-income families reached the highest mean of 3.83% or high level in item no. 7 or providing Technical Assistance to ensure the delivery of programs and projects in the new normal. These findings mean that for respondents ability, from low-income families, utilizing accessible online platforms was a huge challenge, while for those from high-income families, their ability to provide technical assistance was at stake. Research shows that those who are working and those with lower socioeconomic status may have more difficulty practicing recommended behaviors and be required to engage in more risky behaviors. (Kim & Crimmins, 2020)

Table 15

Level of Difficulties Encountered by Student Leaders in the New Normal According to Attitude in terms of Average Family Monthly Income

Items	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a student leader, I encounter difficulties in ...</i>				
1. Upholding the DepEd Core Values in the new normal.	3.33	Moderate Level	3.61	High Level
2. Prioritizing honesty at all times.	3.51	High Level	3.63	High Level
3. Doing the best that I can to ensure the well-being of other students in the new normal education.	3.49	Moderate Level	3.78	High Level
4. Managing my time and energy wisely in the new normal.	3.62	High Level	3.83	High Level
5. Making a commitment to self-improvement.	3.42	Moderate Level	3.65	High Level
6. Showing willingness to embrace opportunities in the new normal.	3.33	Moderate Level	3.67	High Level
7. Adapting to change and even pushing change forward.	3.27	Moderate Level	3.57	High Level

8. Rewarding and recognizing the excellent action of the team.	3.27	Moderate Level	3.67	High Level
9. Valuing the interconnectedness of the team.	3.42	Moderate Level	3.65	High Level
10. Taking advantage of the situation into opportunity in the new normal.	3.47	Moderate Level	3.46	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.41	Moderate Level	3.65	High Level

The table above presented the results of the level of difficulties encountered by student leaders according to area attitude when grouped in terms of average family monthly income. Overall, the data showed a moderate level of difficulty with an overall mean score of 3.41%, obtained by the respondents with low monthly incomes, while those from high-income families had a high level of difficulty with an overall mean score of 3.65%. Moreover, the data showed that the respondents from low-income families obtained the lowest mean of 3.27% or moderate level in item no. 7 or adapting to change and even pushing change forward, and 8 or rewarding and recognizing the excellent action of the team. The respondents from high-income families got the lowest mean of 3.46% or moderate level in item no. 10 or taking advantage of the situation into opportunity in the new normal. It is worth noting that both the respondents with low monthly family income and those with high monthly family income attained the highest mean of 3.62% or high level and 3.83% or high level, respectively, in item no. 4 or managing their time and energy wisely in the new normal. Thus, these outcomes suggested that either low or high monthly family income, respondents' attitudes toward managing their time and staying active online pose a great difficulty. Further, this result conforms to Hodges et al. (2020), whose study explained that the urgent imperative to move online following the virus outbreak forced digital learning upon unprepared school systems.

Table 16

Difference in the Level of Difficulties Encountered by Student Leaders in the New Normal According to the Area Knowledge According to Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U test	Kruskal-Whallis test H	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	49	49.44	860.50		0.179		Not Significant
	Older	42	41.99					
Sex	Male	23	46.50	770.50		0.916		Not Significant
	Female	68	45.83					
School Category	Small	29	38.57		3.413	0.182	0.05	Not Significant
	Medium	39	49.94					
	Large/Mega	23	48.70					
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	45	45.96	1033.00		0.987		Not Significant
	Higher	46	46.04					

Table 16 displays the results of the significant difference in the level of difficulties encountered by student leaders in the new normal according to knowledge when grouped in terms of the aforementioned variables. In general, there was no significant difference in terms of knowledge when grouped and compared to age, sex, school category, and average family monthly income. Moreover, the younger and older respondents obtained a U-test score of 860.5 and a p-value of 0.179, and male and female respondents got a U-test score of 770.50 with a p-value of 0.916. Respondents from small, medium, and large/mega schools obtained an h-test score of 3.413 with a p-value of 0.185, and the respondents with low and high family monthly income got a u-test score of 1,033.00 with a p-value of 0.987. Thus, the obtained p-values were higher than the alpha level of 0.05 and were not significant. Hence, the null hypothesis states that there is no significant difference in the level of difficulties encountered by student leaders in the new normal when grouped according to age, sex, school category, and average family monthly income accepted.

Table 17

Difference in the Level of Difficulties Encountered by Student Leaders in the New Normal According to the Area Ability According to Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney test	U	Kruskal-Whallis test	H	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	49	48.03	929.50				0.428	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	42	43.63							
Sex	Male	23	48.57	723.00				0.589	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	68	45.13							
School Category	Small	29	39.19			3.243		0.198	0.05	Not Significant
	Medium	39	47.55							
	Large/Mega	23	51.96							
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	45	42.78	890.00				0.249	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	46	49.15							

Table 17 revealed the results of the significant difference in the level of difficulties encountered by student leaders in the new normal according to ability when grouped in terms of the aforementioned variables. Generally, there was no significant difference in terms of ability when grouped and compared to age, sex, school category, and average family monthly income. The data showed that the younger and older respondents obtained a u-test score of 929.5 and a p-value of 0.428, male and female respondents got a u-test score of 723.00 with a p-value of 0.589, respondents from small, medium, and large/mega schools obtained a h-test score of 3.243 with a p-value of 0.198, and the respondents with low and high family monthly income got a u-test score of 890.00 with a p-value of 0.249. Thus, all attained p-values were higher than the alpha level of 0.05 and were not significant. Hence, the null hypothesis states that there is no significant difference in the level of difficulties encountered by student leaders in the new normal in terms of ability when they are grouped according to age, sex, school category, and average family monthly income, is accepted.

Table 18

Difference in the Level of Difficulties Encountered by Student Leaders in the New Normal According to Attitude in terms of Age, Sex, School Category, and Average Family Monthly Income

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney test	U	Kruskal-Whallis test	H	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	49	50.49	809.00				0.079	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	42	40.76							
Sex	Male	23	43.70	729.00				0.628	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	68	46.78							
School Category	Small	29	42.69			1.907		0.385	0.05	Not Significant
	Medium	39	44.69							
	Large/Mega	23	52.39							
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	45	43.43	919.50				0.358	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	46	48.51							

Table 18 above exhibited the results of the significant difference in the level of difficulties encountered by student leaders in the new normal according to attitude when grouped in terms of the aforementioned variables. In general, there was no significant difference in terms of attitude when grouped and compared to age, sex, school category, and average family monthly income. Moreover, the younger and older respondents attained a u-test score of 809.00 and a p-value of 0.079, the male and female respondents got a u-test score of 729.00 with a p-value of 0.628, the respondents from small, medium, and large/mega schools obtained a h-test score of 1.907 with a p-value of 0.385, and the respondents with low and high family monthly income got a u-test score of 919.50 with a p-value of 0.358. Consequently, all the p-values were higher than the alpha level of 0.05 and were not significant. Further, the null hypothesis states that there is no significant difference in the level of difficulties encountered by student leaders in the new normal according to attitude when grouped according to age, sex, school category, and average family monthly income, is accepted.

This was proved by the p-values of 0.079, 0.628, 0.385, and 0.249 respectively, which are more significant than 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis states that there is no significant difference in the level of difficulties encountered by student leaders in the new normal when grouped according to age, sex, school category, and average family monthly income accepted. This reveals that the level of difficulties encountered by student leaders in the new normal does not significantly differ according to the area of knowledge; online learning and teaching show that they are effective only if students have consistent access to the internet and computers and if teachers have received targeted training and support for online instruction. Because these needed requirements for effectiveness have been largely absent for many, remote education during the pandemic has impeded teaching and learning. Research on homeschooling shows that it works well for students for whom intentional, personalized, and sufficient resources are available. The crisis-induced delivery of homeschooling without time for planning around children's learning styles and circumstances means that many home-schooled children during the pandemic are not replicating such models, thus not reaping the associated benefits (Garcia & Weiss, 2020).

Conclusions:

Based on the summary of the findings, the researcher draws the following conclusions: It was concluded that student leaders were not cognitively prepared, and the presence of limited resources and accessibility compromised planning, organizing, and implementing activities through online platforms.

Additionally, a conclusion was drawn that regardless of their age, sex, school category, and average monthly family income, the student leaders encountered a high level of difficulties during the pandemic that affected their knowledge, ability, and attitude.

Further, it was concluded that differences in knowledge, ability, and attitude do not significantly affect the difficulty encountered by the respondents in the new normal, particularly in terms of age, sex, school category, and the family's average monthly income.

Recommendations

Based on the summary of findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are advanced: It is recommended that private secondary schools be included as one of the variables to identify differences. Also, future researchers will conduct the same study and explore other areas that were not identified in the present study.

Additionally, it was recommended that student leaders should explore and learn other skills in using online platforms in conducting their activities through online or in-house training during their term of office before the academic calendar.

Also, it was recommended that student councils and the school as a whole implement a project that will provide free access to the internet and equipment in partnership with the Local Government Unit and other stakeholders during their term of office.

Likewise, the Youth Formation Division, School Heads, and Teacher-Advisers shall conduct training on practical concepts and practices on information and communications technology for the students, regardless of their social status, to enhance their knowledge and skills about digital platforms, time management, and leadership enhancement activities during the school calendar.

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